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Abstract:

Deliverable reports on the use of machine translation and post-editing in the translation of survey questionnaires, explored in two experiments. The experiments were conducted in the language pairs English (source)-German (target) and English (source)-Russian (target), the texts are sampled from ESS and EVS questionnaires.

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Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
ESS ERIC/ UPF	Zavala-Rojas, Diana	Diana.zavala@upf.edu
ESS ERIC/ GESIS	Dorer, Brita	brita.dorer@gesis.org
ESS ERIC/ UPF	Sorato, Danielly	danielly.sorato@upf.edu
ESS ERIC/ GESIS	Keck, Veronika	veronikakeck@mailbox.org
ESS ERIC/ GESIS	Behr, Dorothee	dorothee.behr@gesis.org

Contributions of authors

D. Zavala-Rojas (PI) was involved in conceptualization, funding acquisition, project administration, supervision, methodology, formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, data curation.

B. Dorer was involved in conceptualization, funding acquisition, methodology, qualitative analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

D. Sorato was involved in methodology, software, formal analysis, data extraction and processing, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, data curation.

V. Keck was involved in methodology, software, investigation, qualitative analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

D. Behr was involved in conceptualization, funding acquisition, project administration, supervision, methodology, qualitative analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, data curation.

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Executive Summary

In the SSHOC project, European Social Survey (ESS) researchers led a pioneer pilot research project to test for machine translation and post-editing in the translation of survey questionnaires. A highly controlled experimental setting using 40 survey questions from ESS, and European Values Survey (EVS) was used to test the effects of machine translation and post-editing in the Translation, Review, Adjudication, Pretesting and Documentation (TRAPD) approach in survey translation¹. Four experiments were conducted in total, two concerning the language pair English-German and two in the language pair English-Russian. The first configuration of the experiments in each language pair allowed testing for the use of machine translation with *light* human post-editing against a control group in which only human translation was used. The second configuration allowed testing machine translation with *full* human post-editing against the human-translation method control group. Light post-editing implies producing an output that is accurate and comprehensible, but not necessarily stylistically or grammatically adequate. Full post-editing covers the production of output that is accurate, comprehensible, and stylistically adequate, aiming for a human-like translation.

The overall results of this pilot study are positive for the use of machine translation and post-editing in the translation of survey questionnaires with the TRAPD approach; however, specific experiments cannot be generalized out of the context in which the tests took place. The specific experiments reported in this deliverable show evidence that in German and Russian languages and for a sample of ESS and EVS survey questions, the effect of machine translation and post-editing on the quality of the final review translations - with quality understood as texts output with fewest errors as possible - can hardly be distinguished from the quality that derives from using human translations only. Although there is a statistically significant positive increase in the number of errors when light post-editing was used in German, the predicted increase of such errors is 2 units.

In the experiments, the post-editing was implemented by participants whose background is social sciences. This shows positive evidence that machine translation and post-editing can be used in the TRAPD approach by team members whose background is not professional translation. The text outputs analysed in this report are those considered final after the committee meeting, that is, at the review step in the TRAPD approach. The findings show that the committee meeting is a very important aspect of the TRAPD, as the potential effect of methods used in the parallel translations, T step, do not remain in the final outputs.

¹ The team took the TRAPD approach as the translation model but have to acknowledge that pre-testing was not part of the experiment.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

BDÜ	German Federal Association of Interpreters and Translators
BEEPS	Business Environment and Enterprise Performance Survey
CAT	Computer Aided Translation
DQF	Dynamic Quality Framework
EBRD	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
ECB	European Central Bank
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESS ERIC	European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure
ESS	European Social Survey
EVS	European Values Study
EWCS	European Working Conditions Surveys
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
GESIS	Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
HAMT	Human-Aided Machine Translation
HT	Human Translation
ISSP	International Social Survey Programme
LSP	Language Service Provider
MQM-DQF	Multidimensional Quality Metric- Dynamic Quality Framework
MT	Machine translation
N/A	Not applicable
NRS	National Readership Survey
PE	Post-editing
PIAAC	Programme for the International Assessment of Adult Competencies)
PISA	Programme for International Student Assessment
QE	Quality Estimation
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

TAUS	Translation Automation User Society
TRAPD	Translation, Review, Adjudication, Pretesting and Documentation
UPF	Universitat Pompeu Fabra

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1. Introduction

The analysis of natural language by computational means has evolved rapidly in the last two decades. Machine translation (MT) accuracy and fluency has improved substantially after the development of artificial neural network-based engines, and the availability of open-access machine translation tools for the public at large allowed it to become a commonly used internet-based service. Concurrently, *survey translation*, i.e. the translation and translation assessment of survey questionnaires, consolidated as an important area of comparative survey methodology given its large impact on data quality².

The Translation, Review, Adjudication, Pretesting, and Documentation (TRAPD) team approach to survey translation³ has become a gold standard in survey translation, and variants of it are used to translate questionnaires in multilingual projects such as the ESS⁴, the Eurofound surveys⁵, EVS⁶, and SHARE⁷. Team approaches based on the TRAPD have also been applied to the translation of questionnaires in medical and health research⁸ or in market research^{9,10}. Prior to this research project, the use of MT has been discouraged in best-practice guidelines for cross-national survey methodology¹¹. To the best of the

² Janet A. Harkness et al., "Comparative Survey Methodology," in *Survey Methods in Multinational, Multiregional, and Multicultural Contexts*, ed. Janet A. Harkness et al. (John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2010), 1–16, <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470609927.ch1>.

³ Janet A. Harkness, "Questionnaire Translation," in *Cross-Cultural Survey Methods*, ed. Janet A. Harkness, F. J. R. van de Vijver, and P. P. Mohler (Hoboken: Wiley & Sons, 2003), 35–56.

⁴ European Social Survey, "European Social Survey," 2016, <http://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/>.

⁵ Ipsos, "6th European Working Conditions Survey Translation Report," *European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions*, 2015.

⁶ Danuta Przepiórkowska and Dorothee Behr, "European Values Study Translation Guidelines" (Mannheim, Germany, 2017).

⁷ Janet A. Harkness, "SHARE Translation Procedures and Translation Assessment," in *The Survey of Health, Aging, and Retirement in Europe - Methodology*, ed. Alex Borsch-Supan and Henrik Jurges (Mannheim, Germany: Mannheim Research Institute for the Economics of Aging (MEA), 2005), 24–27.

⁸ Barbara H. Forsyth, Martha Stapleton Kudela, Kerry Levin, Deirdre Lawrence, and Gordon B. Willis. "Methods for Translating an English-Language Survey Questionnaire on Tobacco Use into Mandarin, Cantonese, Korean, and Vietnamese." *Field Methods* 19, no. 3 (August 1, 2007): 264–83, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1525822X07302105>.

⁹ Mandy Sha and Jennie Lai, "A Case Study of Improving and Evaluating Consumer Survey Translation," *Translation & Interpreting* 8, no. 1 (2016): 86–100, <https://doi.org/10.12807/ti.108201.2016.a06>.

¹⁰ Diana Kietzmann et al., "Migration Background and Overall Satisfaction with Pre-Hospital Emergency Care," *Applied Nursing Research* 29 (2016): 96–100, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apnr.2015.05.009>.

¹¹ Peter Ph. Mohler et al., "Translation," in *Guidelines for Best Practice in Cross-Cultural Surveys*, ed. Survey Research Center, Second (Ann Arbor, MI: Survey Research Center, Institute for Social Research, University of Michigan, 2016), 233–377, <http://ccsg.isr.umich.edu/index.php/chapters/translation-chapter>.

team's knowledge, so far there have been no recommendations for the use of Human-Aided Machine Translation (HAMT i.e. machine translation with human post-editing, that is a correction of the machine-translated text) for survey translations, at least in the field of academic social sciences surveys. At the same time, however, team acknowledges that MT is slowly entering the field of measurement instruments and is undergoing various tests of applicability^{12,13}.

In the SSHOC Task 4.3: *Applying Computer Assisted Translation in Social Surveys*¹⁴, ESS ERIC researchers (at GESIS and UPF) led a pioneer pilot research project to test for HAMT while implementing the TRAPD approach to survey translation. A highly controlled experimental setting using 40 survey questions from ESS and EVS was used to test the effects of HAMT in survey translation. Four experiments were conducted in total, two concerning the language pair English-German and two in the language pair English-Russian. The first configuration of the experiments in each language pair allowed testing for the use of machine translation with *light* human post-editing against a control group in which only human translation was used. The second configuration tested machine translation with *full* human post-editing against the human-translation method control group. Full post-editing covers the production of accurate, comprehensible and linguistically correct output that is similar or equal to human translation quality. Light post-editing implies producing an output that is accurate and comprehensible, but not necessarily stylistically or grammatically adequate¹⁵.

In the life cycle of survey projects, testing for the impact of new procedures before adopting them is fundamental to maintain survey data quality as teams should control for unknown potential sources of error¹⁶. Ideally, innovations in survey translation should be tested as other methodological innovations, using experimental research¹⁷. In the present report, the ESS ERIC researchers focus on research questions that concern the effect of HAMT in the translation output at the review step of the TRAPD.

This report is organised as follows: The next section reviews academic literature to provide an introduction to machine translation and post-editing, to the TRAPD method, and to translation quality assessment. Thereafter, the research questions are presented. The *Method* section presents in detail the

¹² Himel Mondal, Shaikat Mondal, and Sarika Mondal, "Feasibility of Using 'Google Translate' in Adaptation of Survey Questionnaire from English to Bengali: A Pilot Study," *Indian Journal of Social Psychiatry* 35, no. 2 (2019): 119–24.

¹³ Ritsuko Iwai et al., "Applying Machine Translation to Psychology: Automatic Translation of Personality Adjectives," in *Proceedings of Machine Translation Summit XVII Volume 2: Translator, Project and User Tracks*, 2019, 23–29.

¹⁴ "Computer-assisted translation" is a designation generally used for productivity tools, "machine translation" itself stands for automated translation.

¹⁵ Isabella Massardo et al., "MT Post-Editing Guidelines." TAUS. 2016, <https://info.taus.net/mt-post-editing-guidelines>.

¹⁶ Norbert Schwarz, "Cognitive Aspects of Survey Methodology," *Applied Cognitive Psychology* 21, no. 2 (2007): 277–87.

¹⁷ Diana Zavala-Rojas, "Computational and Corpus Linguistic Tools in Questionnaire Translation: Guidelines to Adopt and Test for Innovations in Survey Translation," 2019, www.seriss.eu/resources/deliverables.

design of the experiments, participants, languages, sample of survey questions, and data collection. The *Analytical approach* section summarizes the error scheme used to evaluate the quality of the translated texts and the error coding approach. The *Results* section presents exploratory analysis and main results of the experiments. Finally, the *Conclusion* section provides an interpretation of the results.

1.1 Literature review

In this section, the research team relates the experiments conducted in this Task to previous work conducted in the area of translation studies and survey translation. First, the report contextualizes MT and post-editing for survey researchers. Subsequently, it describes TRAPD, a gold standard approach to translate survey questionnaires. Finally, the team provides an introduction to translation quality assessment.

1.1.1 Machine translation and post-editing in context

Machine translation is a highly interdisciplinary field whereby translation scholars, engineers, computer scientists, mathematicians, statisticians, and linguists share research objectives. There is a distinction between machine translation ‘tools’, that is, end users’ software that conducts instant machine translation such as Google Translate or DeepL, and machine translation ‘systems’, that is, the implementation of computational approaches for machine translation. In many fields, machine translation outputs are considered pre-translations or draft translations because they typically need revisions by a human translator. In translation practice, machine translation is rarely used in isolation for sensitive materials or publication-grade documents; it is commonly implemented in combination with post-editing. It is possible to distinguish between light and full post-editing, as described above. Thus, it is more accurate to define it as human-aided machine translation (HAMT)¹⁸.

Until recently, the language service provider (LSP) community’s acceptance of machine translation was low; acceptance has become more widespread since the emergence of the neural networks

¹⁸ Chan Sin-wai, *The Future of Translation Technology: Towards a World without Babel*, First, Routledge Studies in Translation Technology (Routledge New York, 2017), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10590-017-9199-x>.

paradigm^{19,20}. Findings from the European Language Industry Survey (2020)²¹ show that MT and PE are further gaining ground and are also considered to be the main trend for the future. Burchardt et al.²² argue that although machine translation engines are gaining acceptance in the translation industry, future successful tools will still require features of automated recognition and classification of machine translation outputs in at least three categories: 1) Output that can be used as is, 2) Machine translation outputs that can easily be post-edited to meet quality specifications, and, 3) Output that should be discarded because post-editing is too time-consuming. The latter would mean that translators should translate from scratch rather than basing their translation on any MT input.

The past two decades have seen a rise in research on machine translation and post-editing, with the trend unhalted; different strands of research can be distinguished; they are not exclusive and are often combined. Currently, a large amount of research focuses on comparing human translation approaches against machine translation and post-editing tasks in translation projects^{23,24}. Researchers have tackled *productivity* (also called processing speed or temporal effort) since this is a major concern for the translation industry – after all, higher productivity is potentially linked to a decrease in costs and/or an increase in the translation volume; Daems, Vandepitte, Hartsuiker, and Macken²⁵, for instance, find that usage of machine translation increased productivity compared to human translation, while Jia, Carl, and Wang²⁶ warn against universal conclusions, since also the text genre needs to be taken into account. In

¹⁹ Dzmitry Bahdanau, Kyung Hyun Cho, and Yoshua Bengio, “Neural Machine Translation by Jointly Learning to Align and Translate,” in *3rd International Conference on Learning Representations, ICLR 2015 - Conference Track Proceedings*, 2015, <http://arxiv.org/abs/1409.0473>.

²⁰ Joss Moorkens, “What to Expect from Neural Machine Translation: A Practical in-Class Translation Evaluation Exercise,” *Interpreter and Translator Trainer* 12, no. 4 (2018): 375–87, <https://doi.org/10.1080/1750399X.2018.1501639>.

²¹ ELIA et al., “European Language Industry Survey 2020: Before & After COVID-19,” 2020, <http://fit-europe-rc.org/en/resources/publications/>.

²² Aljoscha Burchardt et al., “Language Technology Drives Quality Translation,” *MultiLingual* 143, no. 3 (2014): 33–39, https://www.dfki.de/lt/publication_show.php?id=7486.

²³ Ana Guerberof Arenas, “Correlations between Productivity and Quality When Post-Editing in a Professional Context,” *Machine Translation* 28, no. 3–4 (2014): 165–86, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10590-014-9155-y>.

²⁴ Yanfang Jia, Michael Carl, and Xiangling Wang, “How Does the Post-Editing of Neural Machine Translation Compare with from-Scratch Translation? A Product and Process Study,” *Journal of Specialised Translation* 31 (2019): 60–86.

²⁵ Joke Daems et al., “Identifying the Machine Translation Error Types with the Greatest Impact on Post-Editing Effort,” *Frontiers in Psychology* 8, no. August (August 2, 2017): 1282, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01282>.

²⁶ Yanfang Jia, Michael Carl, and Xiangling Wang, “How Does the Post-Editing of Neural Machine Translation Compare with from-Scratch Translation? A Product and Process Study,” *Journal of Specialised Translation* 31 (2019): 60–86.

Koponen's²⁷ literature review, statistical and/or rule-based MT systems appear to yield mixed results, which is due to different language pairs, different text genres investigated, and systems fine-tuned (or not) for a certain text genre.

Beyond productivity, the topic of *quality* (also called product quality) is assessed from different angles. Different machine translation systems are compared, with the latest neural machine translation paradigm running against its predecessors, in particular the statistical machine translation method^{28,29,30,31}. This research may be combined (as these researchers do) with testing the different machine translation systems on different or rare languages to take account of the fact that machine translation quality is (still) linked to both the system employed and the language pair under investigation. Knowledge on the kind of errors that need to be corrected and necessary system improvements results from such research studies. Moreover, post-editing and human translations are compared using criteria such as fluency, accuracy, acceptability, and adequacy³², or focusing on the concept of *post-editese*, which postulates that human translation and post-editing *are* different^{33,34}. Research also focuses on evaluating the usability of machine translation outputs across languages. Doherty and O'Brien³⁵ concluded that the usability of such outputs is, in fact, dependent on the language pairs. They studied a source language,

²⁷ Maarit Koponen, "Is Machine Translation Post-Editing Worth the Effort? A Survey of Research into Post-Editing and Effort," *The Journal of Specialised Translation* 25 (2016): 131–48.

²⁸ Sheila Castilho et al., "A Comparative Quality Evaluation of PBSMT and NMT Using Professional Translators A Comparative Quality Evaluation of PBSMT and NMT Using Professional Translators," *Proceedings of MT Summit XVI, the 16th Machine Translation Summit*, no. September (2017), <http://tramooc.eu>.

²⁹ Rejwanul Haque, Mohammed Hasanuzzaman, and Andy Way, "Investigating Terminology Translation in Statistical and Neural Machine Translation: A Case Study on English-to-Hindi and Hindi-to-English," *International Conference Recent Advances in Natural Language Processing, RANLP 2019-Septe*, no. 2017 (2019): 437–46, https://doi.org/10.26615/978-954-452-056-4_052.

³⁰ Maarit Koponen, Leena Salmi, and Markku Nikulin, "A Product and Process Analysis of Post-Editor Corrections on Neural, Statistical and Rule-Based Machine Translation Output," *Machine Translation* 33, (2019): 61–90, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10590-019-09228-7>.

³¹ Maja Popović, "Language-Related Issues for NMT and PBMT for English–German and English–Serbian," *Machine Translation* 32, no. 3 (2018): 237–53, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10590-018-9219-5>.

³² Jia, Carl, and Wang, "How Does the Post-Editing of Neural Machine Translation Compare with from-Scratch Translation? A Product and Process Study."

³³ Antonio Toral, "Post-Editese: An Exacerbated Translationese," 2019, <http://arxiv.org/abs/1907.00900>.

³⁴ Daems et al., "Identifying the Machine Translation Error Types with the Greatest Impact on Post-Editing Effort."

³⁵ Stephen Doherty and Sharon O'Brien, "Assessing the Usability of Raw Machine Translated Output: A User-Centered Study Using Eye Tracking," *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction* 30, no. 1 (2014): 40–51, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2013.802199>.

English, and four *target* languages, that is the translated language: Spanish, French, German, and Japanese, the latter showing a considerably lower usability of machine translation outputs.

A large amount of research focuses on investigating *effort*, stand-alone or in combination with product quality. In his seminal work, Krings³⁶ differentiated between three (inter-related) types of post-editing effort: temporal effort, which is the time spent on post-editing (i.e. productivity); technical effort, which stands for the number of edits made by the post-editor (insertions, deletions, reordering), and cognitive effort, which stands for the mental processes involved when doing post-editing. Numerous researchers base their studies on these dimensions, such as Vieira^{37,38,39}, who looked into cognitive effort and found this type of effort particularly linked to grammar and lexis. Daems, Vandepitte, Hartsuiker, and Macken⁴⁰ found that coherence issues, grammar issues, and meaning shifts can be regarded as good candidates for effort prediction based on MT quality. Moorkens, O'Brien, Silva, Fonseca, and Alves⁴¹ compared human estimated post-editing effort and actual effort and found only little agreement. Studying effort comes into play in the translation industry when certain machine translation proposals may no longer be made, or at least flagged for problems, due to a predicted high cognitive load.

Eventually, the field of machine translation assessment is constantly evolving, making use of (combined) human and automated assessment methods^{42,43}.

³⁶ Hans P. Krings, *Repairing Texts: Empirical Investigations of Machine Translation Post-Editing Processes*, Translation Studies (Kent State University Press, 2001), <https://books.google.es/books?id=vsdPsIXCiWAC>.

³⁷ Lucas Nunes Vieira, "Cognitive Effort and Different Task Foci in Post-Editing of Machine Translation: A Think-Aloud Study," *Across Languages and Cultures* 18, no. 1 (2017): 70–105, <https://doi.org/10.1556/084.2017.18.1.4>.

³⁸ Lucas Nunes Vieira, Elisa Alonso, and Lindsay Bywood, "Post-Editing in Practice - Process, Product and Networks," *Journal of Specialised Translation* 2019, no. 31 (2019): 2–13.

³⁹ Lucas Nunes Vieira, "How Do Measures of Cognitive Effort Relate to Each Other? A Multivariate Analysis of Post-Editing Process Data," *Machine Translation* 30, no. 1–2 (2016): 41–62, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10590-016-9188-5>.

⁴⁰ Daems et al., "Identifying the Machine Translation Error Types with the Greatest Impact on Post-Editing Effort."

⁴¹ Joss Moorkens et al., "Correlations of Perceived Post-Editing Effort with Measurements of Actual Effort," *Machine Translation* 29 (December 1, 2015): 267–84, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10590-015-9175-2>.

⁴² Bonnie Dorr, Matt Snover, and Nitin Madnani, "Part 5: Machine Translation Evaluation," *Handbook of Natural Language Processing and Machine Translation*, no. 1 (2006): 801–94.

⁴³ Renzhong Peng and Mali Tan, "Translation Quality Assessment from Principles to Practice," ed. Stephen Doherty (Eds.) Joss Moorkens, Sheila Castilho, Federico Gaspari (Cham, Switzerland: Elsevier, 2018), 287.

Common to past scholarly work is the use of long texts as the unit of analysis to assess the effects of HMT, such as news articles⁴⁴ or literary works⁴⁵. In the case of survey questionnaires, an individual survey item or question is an extremely short text, often consisting of a few sentences. Therefore, with the present research on questionnaire translation the project team explores the use of HMT in such extremely short texts.

1.1.2 The TRAPD method

The TRAPD method has become the gold standard to translate survey questionnaires in the field of academic social sciences surveys. It is a team or committee approach in a multistep process. Team members provide their specific expertise to arrive at a final translation. The team members should combine survey knowledge, translation and linguistic expertise, knowledge about the culture where the questionnaire will be administered, and potentially other knowledge related to the topic of the survey. The TRAPD method requires that at least two translators ('T' in the acronym) produce independent and parallel translations of the source version into a target language; or that source texts are split among (at least) two translators. In a 'review' meeting, the translations are discussed by the two translators together with a 'reviewer' ('R'); an 'adjudicator' ('A') is responsible for the final decisions on different translation options. Oftentimes, the roles of reviewer and adjudicator are merged. The translated questionnaire is 'pretested' before fieldwork ('P') and the whole process is 'documented' ('D').

1.1.3 Translation quality assessment

Neither in translation studies nor in the translation industry there is unanimity about how to best measure or assess translation quality. There are different approaches and dichotomies along which to choose; as there is not a one-off approach for all translations to assess, it has to be decided for each particular case, depending on aspects such as text genre⁴⁶, audience, and the purpose of the translation.

Firstly, it needs to be clarified whether *translation quality should refer to the translation process or to the textual output resulting from the translation process*, the latter being of main interest to us⁴⁷. In this study, the research team aimed at achieving the best-possible process quality by applying the method that is

⁴⁴ Samuel Lübli, Rico Sennrich, and Martin Volk, "Has Machine Translation Achieved Human Parity? A Case for Document-Level Evaluation," in *Proceedings of the 2018 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing, EMNLP 2018*, 2020, 4791–96, <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/d18-1512>.

⁴⁵ Joss Moorkens et al., "Translators' Perceptions of Literary Post-Editing Using Statistical and Neural Machine Translation," *Translation Spaces* 7 (November 28, 2018): 240–62, <https://doi.org/10.1075/ts.18014.moo>.

⁴⁶ By "text genre" it is referred to different types of written discourse, such as manuals, certificates, poems, or questionnaires. Readers may also have heard the term "text type".

⁴⁷ Daniel Gouadec, "Quality in Translation," *Handbook of Translation Studies* 1 (2010): 270–75.

currently considered to be best practice for translating questionnaires: the TRAPD (see description above), by providing all actors with the support they needed, and by ensuring that also conditions such as payment or deadlines were appropriate and reasonable.

When it comes to assessing the quality of translation outputs, a basic *differentiation for the translation quality assessment method* to choose is between error-based assessments, based on the detection of translation or other types of errors in the target text, and comprehensive approaches additionally including the text function and the relationship between the author and the reader.⁴⁸

Another dichotomy is the *differentiation between relative measures of translation quality* - that is, comparing the quality of different translations to one another - and, on the opposite, *absolute measures of translation quality* in which a translation's quality is assessed on its own, independent of other translations.

Why is assessing a translation's quality so challenging? Different factors come into play, but the most important one is that there is almost never only one correct or perfect translation that may serve as a gold standard that other translations could be compared to. Translation is in most cases not working on one-to-one equivalencies. Moreover, translation changes text: "Translation does inevitably involve some loss, since it is impossible to preserve all the ST [source text] nuances of meaning and structure in the TL [target language]⁴⁹." From the universe of all possible translations, criteria need to be defined about what is to be a *good*, what is an *acceptable*, and what is an *unacceptable* translation. This has to be done for each translated text separately as it may depend on various factors, such as text genre, audience, the quality level required, and intended purpose.

For instance, in some technical fields, such as the legal or the mechanical engineering field, it may be possible to create one reference translation that is correct and meets all terminological and stylistic requirements of a text; for instance, the translation of a birth certificate serving the same purpose in the target language and culture or the manual of a device serving the same purpose in the target language and culture. But even in these text genres that are characterised by a more controlled terminology or style, there may be other solutions that would be as good as the reference one, so there will be more than one perfect reference text to compare to. In other text genres, such as press releases, course books or literary works, there is much more leeway in translation; therefore, there is not a single translation that could serve as the reference.

⁴⁸ Geoffrey S. Koby and Isabel Lacruz, "The Thorny Problem of Translation and Interpreting Quality," *Linguistica Antverpiensia, New Series – Themes in Translation Studies* 16 (2017): 1–12, <https://doi.org/10.52034/lanstts.v16i0.487>.

⁴⁹ Jeremy Munday, *Introducing Translation Studies: Theories and Applications* (Routledge, 2016).

About the question of how to define a *high-quality translation*, there is no unanimity amongst translation scholars and practitioners: Koby et al.⁵⁰, for instance, differentiate between narrower definitions of *good* quality that include the requirement that the message of the source text is correctly rendered without linguistic errors, whereas, according to Koby et al., broader definitions may only require the target text to be fluent and accurate for the target audience, without clear reference to the source text⁵¹. In summary, each field and each particular project in which the quality of one or several translations is to be assessed has to develop their own assessment method and quality thresholds and definitions.

One approach for assessing a translation's quality consists in applying a translation quality model. While also with regard to translation quality models there is no unanimity about which models to apply⁵², a translation quality assessment model prominent in academic translation studies is the one developed and updated by House⁵³. This model is not focussing on determining whether a translation is good or bad. It analyses both the source and the target text based on certain criteria and compares these to one another. House starts from the idea that "A detailed analysis of the 'hows' and the 'whys' of translated texts versus their originals has to be the descriptive foundation for any argued assessment of whether and to what degree a given translation may be seen to be adequate or not."⁵⁴. House's model embeds both the source and target texts into a larger context and analyses the following aspects: *field*, that is, the subject matter and social action linked to the text; *tenor*, the relationship of the actors linked to the text, mainly the author and the readers or audience, but also the commissioner or client, if applicable; *mode*, the way in which the text addresses the readers, such as oral or written, involved or informative, explicit or situation-dependent, or similar. For each of these areas, the model requires analysis of the lexical means, that is, the words chosen, of syntactical elements of the text, as well as, where applicable, the social role of the actors expressed in the text. An additional aspect of this model is the *genre* of the text. While the areas *field*, *tenor*, and *mode* are analysed by the researcher(s) applying the model, assessing the *genre* is supported by the use of Corpora⁵⁵.

⁵⁰ Koby and Lacruz, "The Thorny Problem of Translation and Interpreting Quality."

⁵¹ Geoffrey S. Koby et al., "Defining Translation Quality," *Tradumàtica: Tecnologies de La Traducció*, no. 12 (December 30, 2014): 413–420, <https://doi.org/10.5565/rev/tradumatica.76>.

⁵² Koby and Lacruz, "The Thorny Problem of Translation and Interpreting Quality."

⁵³ Juliane House, *Translation Quality Assessment. {A} Model Revisited* (Tübingen: Narr, 1997).

⁵⁴ Juliane House, "Translation quality assessment: Linguistic description versus social evaluation," *Meta: journal des traducteurs/Meta: translators' Journal*, no. 46(2) (2001): 243–257. (p. 248).

⁵⁵ Eve-Marie Gendron-Pontbriand, "House, Juliane (2015) : Translation quality assessment : past and present. Londres : Routledge, 160 p.," *Meta* 61, no. 2 (August 22, 2016): 481–85, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.7202/1037770ar>.

In the professional context, error typologies are typically used such as the LISA QA model, applied in the IT translation industry in particular, or the SAE J2450 model, developed by the American Society for Automotive Engineers, jointly with General Motors. These typologies typically include a list of errors (e.g., pertaining to the domains language, terminology, and style) and often also allow for the possibility to weigh errors according to a severity level. Applying these models is not error-free since subjective judgement can differ as to whether an error counts as a lexical or a terminological error or how severe it is, for instance. Clear guidelines, training, and regular practice with an error typology are measures to reduce the impact of subjectivity on the coding⁵⁶.

In the present research, the focus is on assessing the quality of the translations agreed on in the review sessions, where one of the two parallel translations was based on MT and post-editing. Thus the focus is on the assessment of the product; moreover, an error typology will be applied, as used in the professional context. This approach is explained in detail in the section *Analytical approach*.

⁵⁶ Gabriela Saldanha and Sharon O'Brien, *Research Methodologies in Translation Studies, Research Methodologies in Translation Studies* (Routledge, 2014), <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315760100>.

2. Research questions

The main focus of this deliverable is to report on the findings of testing experimentally the use of HAMT at the translation and review steps of the TRAPD. The experiments aim at exploring if effects of HAMT can be observed in the translation output at the review step of the TRAPD. Thus, the main research question is: Is the quality of the final review output affected by introducing machine translation and post-editing? If so, are the effects negative or positive for the outputs' quality? Please note that in answering these questions, team is focusing on the quality of the review output, not on the review process as such.

Harkness and other proponents of the TRAPD argued that the review sessions in which the team discusses translation options are fundamental to translation quality^{57,58,59}; for this reason, the Task team chose to assess the effects of MT and post-editing on the output texts *after* the review step. Investigating the impact of introducing MT and post-editing in the translation process as such is not studied in this pilot project. It is a subject matter for future research.

More specific research questions describe group dependencies of the effect of MT and post-editing: Are observed effects conditional on group membership? Group is understood as the combination made up of the language in each experiment and the type of post-editing among light or full post-editing. Therefore, concretely these questions can be framed as: Are Russian and German translations affected differently? And, are the differences conditional on the use of light or full post-editing?

There is evidence about differences in the quality of MT outputs across languages^{60,61}. The experiments in two language pairs are conducted to add evidence to the findings. Furthermore, the type of post-editing can be decisive when it comes to evaluating the impact of HAMT on the final translated text. A growing body of literature using English as source languages and a variety of target languages (e.g. Arabic, Danish, French, German, Latvian, Polish, Spanish, among many others) suggests that machine

⁵⁷ Mohler et al., "Translation."

⁵⁸ Janet A. Harkness, Beth-Ellen Pennell, and Alisú Schoua-Glusberg, "Survey Questionnaire Translation and Assessment," in *Methods for Testing and Evaluating Survey Questionnaires* (John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2004), 453–73, <https://doi.org/10.1002/0471654728.ch22>.

⁵⁹ Janet A. Harkness, Ana Villar, and Brad Edwards, "Translation, Adaptation, and Design," in *Survey Methods in Multinational, Multiregional, and Multicultural Contexts*, ed. Janet A. Harkness et al. (John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2010), 115–40, <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470609927.ch7>.

⁶⁰ Stephen Doherty and Sharon O'Brien. "Assessing the Usability of Raw Machine Translated Output: A User-Centered Study Using Eye Tracking."

⁶¹Castilho et al., "A Comparative Quality Evaluation of PBSMT and NMT Using Professional Translators A Comparative Quality Evaluation of PBSMT and NMT Using Professional Translators."

translation followed by full post-editing does not compromise translation quality, in comparison to a fully human-translation approach; at the same time there are mixed effects with respect to translators' productivity depending on the type of post-editing (Screen 2019)

As introduced in previous sections, the research team in SSHOC Task 4.3: *Applying Computer Assisted Translation in Social Surveys* analysed translation quality based on an error framework. Quality is difficult to quantify, but errors can be categorized, coded, and observed. Therefore, it is assumed that there is an inverse relationship between errors and quality, in which texts presenting fewer errors are of higher quality. Therefore, the following hypotheses for the research question are postulated; these hypotheses applying to each language pair.

For Experiment 1 - inclusion of MT and full post-editing into the process:

Null hypothesis (H0): There is no difference in the number of errors in the output texts after the review session in the control group in comparison with the group using MT and *full* post-editing

Alternative hypothesis (H1): There is a significant difference in the number of errors in the output texts after the review session in the control group in comparison with the group using MT and *full* post-editing

For Experiment 2 - inclusion of MT and light post-editing into the process:

H0: There is no difference in the number of errors in the output texts after the review session in the control group in comparison with the group using MT and *light* post-editing

H1: There is a significant difference in the number of errors in the output texts after the review session in the control group in comparison with the group using MT and *light* post-editing

3. Method

3.1 Research design

The team designed and conducted four translation experiments to test for the impact of HAMT in the outputs produced at the review step of the TRAPD. The team used a design in which a language-specific control group, with three participants, G^k_0 , implements the translation (T) and review (R) steps of the TRAPD without using machine translation at all. The language pair used in the experiments is indicated by, $k = \{0, 1\}$, where 0 indicates English-German and 1, English-Russian. The team in the control group is built up by two human translators HT_{00} and HT_{10} and a reviewer R_{00} . This control group simulates a generic form of the process implemented by survey projects at present. The control group is compared against two treatment groups, G^k_1 and G^k_2 . In the first treatment G^k_1 , at the translation step, one translation was conducted by a human translator denoted by HT_{21} , and the second translation was obtained when a post-editor, PE_{01} , who received a machine-translated output, conducted *full* post-editing. The reviewer is denoted as R_{11} . In the second treatment G^k_2 , the first translation was also human-produced, denoted as HT_{32} , and the second input translation for the review session was obtained by a post-editor using a *light* post-edited version of the machine-translated text, denoted as PE_{12} . As in the other groups, there is a reviewer denoted as R_{22} . Each participant was only assigned to one group and one role. Control and treatment groups shared all other features except for the interventions defined here as it will be described in detail in the next subsections.

In the review session, each group or team finalized a set of \mathbf{y} translated segments (i.e. translation units such as a sentence or a response option, typically delimited by a full stop, a question mark or a line break), each segment denoted by y^k_{ij} , with $i = 0, 1, \dots, 267$; indicating one out of 268 segments of 40 survey questions sampled from the ESS and the EVS questionnaires. The subscript $j = 0, 1, 2$, indicates that the participant was part of the control group, first treatment using full post-editing or the second treatment using light post-editing, respectively. In all groups, the first input translation was made by a professional translator, and the second by a social scientist. Therefore, the effects of the participant background are intertwined by design with the method they use; for instance, treatment G^k_1 , studies the combination of MT, full post-editing and a translator with a background in social sciences.

$$G^k_0 = \{\text{Human Translator (HT)}_{00}, HT_{10}, \text{Reviewer (R}_{00})\} \quad \boxed{\leftrightarrow} \mathbf{y}^k = y^k_{00, \dots, y^k_{i0}} \mid i=0, 1, \dots, 267 \text{ and } j=0 \text{ and } k=0, 1$$

$$G^k_1 = \{HT_{21}, PE_{01}, R_{11}\} \quad \boxed{\leftrightarrow} \mathbf{y}^k = \mathbf{y}^k = y^k_{01, \dots, y^k_{i1}} \mid i=0, 1, \dots, 267 \text{ and } j=1 \text{ and } k=0, 1$$

$$G^k_2 = \{HT_{32}, PE_{12}, R_{22}\} \quad \boxed{\leftrightarrow} \mathbf{y}^k = \mathbf{y}^k = y^k_{02, \dots, y^k_{i2}} \mid i=0, 1, \dots, 267 \text{ and } j=2 \text{ and } k=0, 1$$

Figures 1-3 below summarize the design of the experiments, and the subsections below describe in detail all their features.

FIGURE 1: SUMMARY OF THE CONTROL GROUP

FIGURE 2: SUMMARY OF THE TREATMENT USING FULL POST-EDITING

FIGURE 3: SUMMARY OF THE TREATMENT USING LIGHT POST-EDITING

3.2 Language choice

The experiments were implemented in two language pairs, English into German and Russian, respectively. These languages were chosen for the following reasons: They are both languages that are used in several countries in large-scale cross-national European survey research. For instance, Russian has been used in the ESS in Estonia, Georgia, Israel, Latvia, Lithuania, Russia, and Ukraine. German has been used in the ESS in Austria, Germany, Luxembourg, and Switzerland. Furthermore, both languages stand for different language families, Russian being a member of the Slavic language family, and German being a member of the Proto-Germanic language family. Against the backdrop that machine translation quality is (still) dependent on the language pair, this combination of language pairs allows us to assess potentially different mechanisms as well as acceptance of MT. Ultimately and in practical terms, the native languages of the research team also played a role in the language choice.

3.3 Participants

The following criteria was specified for the study participants: Human translators HT_{00} , HT_{21} and HT_{32} (the left side in visual terms in the Figures above) had to be professional translators, with at least 5 years of translation practice and previous experience translating survey questionnaires. Human translator HT_{10} and post-editors PE_{01} and PE_{12} had to be social scientists, with at least 2 years of work experience in the social sciences, with experience in questionnaire design, and with translation experience. Reviewers R_{00} , R_{11} , and R_{21} had to be social scientists, too, with work experience in the social sciences of at least 5 years. Those were targeted as reviewers who had already had some experience in review sessions, ideally as

lead, and/or those who would be willing to lead a review session. They also had to have experience in questionnaire design.

Participants were native speakers⁶² of either German or Russian, *k*. The combination of having both professional translators and social scientists collaborating in teams goes back to how the interdisciplinary TRAPD model is set-up⁶³. Rather than having two professional translators at the translation stage, the team opted for a mixed approach, since the reality in many social science survey projects is that project team members (that is, usually social scientists) will be involved in the translation process. Participants had fixed role-background combinations; that means, for each role in the experiments, a certain set of backgrounds and skills was required.

The research team used its own networks, snowball sampling, a professional website targeting freelance translators (Proz.com), the German Federal Association of Interpreters and Translators (BDÜ), the Union of Translators of Russia, the National League of Translators and Interpreters in Russia, independent, non-governmental polling and sociological research organizations (e.g. Levada Center), and major international surveys (e.g. International Social Survey Programme (ISSP), The Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement (SHARE)) to invite potential participants to fill in a recruitment questionnaire, including questions on a university degree, job, experience with questionnaire translation, with questionnaire design, familiarity with translation tools, availability, and remuneration. In total, 28 responses from social scientists were received and 43 responses from professional translators. Based on the results, the team matched backgrounds and experiences so that the teams of the control group and the full post-editing or light post-editing treatments were, across languages, similar in terms of team composition, backgrounds, and skills. Across the groups, characteristics of the participants were standardized to the maximum extent; however, some features were not possible such as years of experience in survey translation.

All 18 approved participants were paid for their tasks. All participants were given information on data protection and asked for their written informed consent prior to taking part in the study. In the data protection document, participants were informed that “[t]he study aim is to integrate machine translation into team-based questionnaire translation procedures and to evaluate the overall process”; they were not informed on and neither requested further details of the study. In the training (see next subsection), they received information on their particular team, but not in relation to the overall study design.

⁶² One reviewer had a native speaker competence of the target language and was frequently responsible for review sessions in this language, even though not having, strictly speaking, this language as a mother tongue. Russian native speakers came from different Russian-speaking countries. The language version for the final review translation, if adaptation were found to be needed, was fixed to be the reviewer language.

⁶³ Harkness, “Questionnaire Translation.”

The following Table 1 sums up key characteristics of the participants:

TABLE 1: SELECTED CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PARTICIPANTS

Background and experience	Social scientists (n = 12)	Professional translators (n = 6)
Sex	3 male, 9 female	2 male, 4 female
Age	average 43 years old	average 44 years old
work experience in the social sciences	average 16 years	Not applicable (N/A)
work experience as a professional translator	N/A	average 16 years
experience either translating or reviewing or proofreading survey questionnaires	all 12 participants	all 6 participants
experience in questionnaire development/design	12	N/A
experience in leading review sessions	2 participants (reviewers) out of 12	N/A
experience using the CAT tool MateCat	none	none

3.4 Training of participants

Protocols were prepared for each role and participants received online training of 2 to 2.5 hours to conduct their tasks. Training for (1) human translators, both professional translators and social scientists; (2) post-editors, both full and light post-editing, and (3) reviewers was differentiated. They all received a common core, such as information on the implemented TRA(PD) model, a translation brief (goal of translation, target group, survey mode), general *do's* and *don'ts* in questionnaire translation, and information on the source questionnaire. They were instructed to avoid looking up existing ESS and EVS translations online. Post-editors received additional training on their full and light post-editing task, respectively; translators and post-editors all received training on how to translate or post-edit in the translation tool MateCat. After the online training, the participants received a PDF containing all slides

from the presentations, guidelines on the use of MateCat (if applicable to the role), as well as a checklist for full and light post-editing with examples (if applicable to the role).

3.5 Selection of survey questions

The selection of the survey questions was done by a combination of random sampling and qualitative considerations. This twofold approach ensured randomness in the selection of questions to be translated and coverage of key characteristics and potential translation challenges of a survey questionnaire. The research team listed unique⁶⁴ questions included in the questionnaires of Round 1 (dated in 2002) to Round 9 (2018) of the ESS, resulting in 1,454 questions. From the EVS, the sampling frame included Wave 1 (1981) to Wave 5 (2017), resulting in 1,745 questions. In total, there were 3,199 unique questions. The team then sampled 262 survey questions stratified by wave/round and study.

TABLE 2: DISTRIBUTION OF THE SAMPLE OF QUESTIONS FROM ESS AND EVS

Study	Round	Percentage	Questions sampled
ESS	R1	9%	24
ESS	R2	7%	17
ESS	R3	4%	11
ESS	R4	4%	11
ESS	R5	5%	12
ESS	R6	4%	10
ESS	R7	3%	10
ESS	R8	2%	10
ESS	R9	2%	10
EVS	W1	11%	26
EVS	W2	22%	54
EVS	W3	9%	23
EVS	W4	11%	26
EVS	W5	7%	18
		100%	262

⁶⁴ The ESS has a “core” questionnaire that is repeated in each round; this core questionnaire was only included once in the sampling frame to prevent having repeated questions.

Starting from this random sample, a final set of 40 questions was selected by evaluating each of the questions in the sample against a predefined set of criteria, and attributing them a prioritization level. The criteria considered typical problems in human questionnaire translation, for instance, answer categories embedded in a longer sentence, consistency between question stem and answer categories, or gender issues. The criteria also included cases where machine translation was expected to be more problematic than human translation. In summary, the selection was partly based on known difficulties in questionnaire translation and partly focussed on known machine translation difficulties. In total, the 40 questions constituted 268 segments, *y* (as defined in the section *Research design*).

To arrive at the 40 items, three researchers of the team evaluated all items individually and then met to agree on the item selection. Some items had a lower priority level, but the team selected them nevertheless to create a smooth source questionnaire without breaks, for instance, for filling *batteries* with more than one item. Table 3 below summarizes the criteria; marked with an asterisk are criteria that are related to problems in machine translation.

As the questionnaires to be translated should in principle function as a coherent measurement instrument, a few modifications were introduced to the original source items to create a lab questionnaire. For instance, Don't know and Refusal categories were harmonised across ESS and EVS items.

TABLE 3: ITEM EVALUATION AND SELECTION CRITERIA

Category	Examples of sub-categories
Annotation⁶⁵	With/without annotation
Challenging terminology/wording	Terms related to one's feelings, state of mind, well-being (e.g., feeling depressed, lonely)
	Tricky term/wording, incl. known challenges (e.g. government, family) and technical terms that may or may not be adapted to a specific country context (e.g. unemployment benefit)
Source text issues	Ambiguous/unclear wording/item as such

⁶⁵ Dorothee Behr and Evi Scholz, "Questionnaire Translation in Cross-National Survey Research: On the Types and Value of Annotations," *Methoden - Daten - Analysen* 5, no. 2 (2011): 157–79.

	Linguistic distinction challenging (e.g. fair/just)
	(Strongly) idiomatic language in the source, idioms, figure of speech (e.g. worse off; hit and run)
Syntax/grammar/complexity	Response categories and/or items that are part of a longer sentence ("broken stem items")
Challenging survey/design elements	WH word (such as what, who, why) - gradation (i.e. to what extent/degree)
	Balance of request (e.g. do you agree or disagree, feeling better or worse)
	Words providing a framework for the answer (e.g., about, approximate, in general, all in all, ever, any)
	Survey-specific terminology/phrases (e.g. "card", "Read out"; interviewer instruction: "If unclear, repeat the instructions", "if any")
	Fills
Known MT problems	Gender/number/unclear person (1st or 3rd person)
	Addressing persons (e.g. you)
	Subordinate clauses with different subjects: use of pronouns, relative pronouns (i.e. which, who, whose, etc.) in the second sentence (vs. noun in the first sentence)

Note: This is an updated scheme of item selection criteria. Since some categories in the original scheme, particularly related to terminology, were not used consistently, these were merged into one category in an updated scheme.

3.6 Data collection

Data collection took place during the five weeks between September 18th and October 23rd, 2020. Training took place from September 15th to October 8th. The T step (either human translation or machine translation and post-editing) took place from September 18th to October 4th. As the experiments took place in 2020 and in-person meetings were discouraged or not legally allowed worldwide, the training sessions and the review sessions were conducted online using Zoom. All participants answered a questionnaire before the start of the experiment (i.e., before the training) and

after the review session. Participants assigned to the role of post-editors answered an additional questionnaire after completing their post-editing task⁶⁶.

3.7 Translation, post-editing, and review environment

Before the data collection, several computer-aided translation (CAT) tools were considered to be chosen for the experiments: MateCat, OmegaT, and translate5. Based on a set of criteria satisfying the scope of the project, MateCat was selected as an appropriate tool for the human and machine translation, post-editing activities, and review discussion. The main reasons for using MateCat were its integrated, free of charge available machine translation system (Google Translate and Microsoft Translator⁶⁷, post-editing features (time measure, effort measure, difference files), up-to-date design and code, web-based service without download and installation requirements, and simple quality assurance features - such as warnings for issues with tags (i.e., machine-readable formatting of a document), for superfluous white spaces, or translation inconsistencies⁶⁸. A limitation of this study is that only one machine translation engine was used; however, including more than one engine (e.g., additionally deepl) would have multiplied the number of experimental interventions, adding groups to compare among each other. Future research should allow for the comparison of different MT engines.

Prior to the start of the translating and post-editing tasks, a member of the research team prepared the document for translation in a CAT tool and then set up individual translation projects in MateCat; for each participant, project settings were selected in line with their role in the study. Translation annotations (i.e. item-specific guidelines for translation) were manually inserted into MateCat as *comments*, because there is no automatic insertion function for such special support structure in MateCat. The document for the translation was a spreadsheet with no additional text in it, and no meta-data information except for the items for translation in the source English language.

The general settings in MateCat included disabling the translation memory function MyMemory, selected in MateCat by default, in order to avoid inserting not finalised translations to the collaborative generic public translation memory in MateCat. Advanced options were activated for all participants: “guess tag position” that enables MateCat to automatically place the tags where they belong; “linguistic QA checks” automatically checks punctuation, numerals, links, and symbols; segmentation rules “general” split sentences according to specific types of content, e.g. sentence by sentence, expression by expression in

⁶⁶ Analysis of the information provided in the questionnaires is out of the scope of this deliverable.

⁶⁷ “Machine Translation”: <https://guides.matecat.com/my> (2 December, 2021).

⁶⁸ Diana Zavala-Rojas et al., “MS17 Open Source CAT TM Software Selected,” July 31, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4581806>.

case of response options. The settings for the machine translation function were disabled for all, except for the post-editors PE_{01,12} in each treatment group, who received MateCat projects with enabled machine translation settings.

Based on their tasks in the project, the participants worked on different MateCat tabs: the *Translate* tab or the *Revise* tab. All human translators were using the Translate tab to insert their translations from scratch without using any pre-translations. This is not a common scenario in current translation practice, translators usually receive suggestions of pre-translations from translation memory matches or from machine translation, however, in this case, as the purpose of the experiment was to use only human translation in this group, suggestions of pre-translations were excluded by design. All post-editors worked on the Revise tab during their post-editing task because the machine-translated text was inserted automatically on the Translate tab. Post-editor tasks included not only the revision and correction of the machine-translated text but also the selection of an error type for describing the change that the post-editor needed to apply to the raw MT output. MateCat offers five such 'error types' to select from: Translation that includes e.g. semantics and accuracy; Style (e.g. fluency), Language quality (e.g. grammar, syntax, punctuation, etc.), Terminology (includes consistency), and Tags (formatting issues). Post-editors also had to select any of the severity levels Neutral, Minor or Major, which were defined as follows:

- *Major* level of severity means that the translation completely changes the meaning, likely misleads the respondent, or provides incorrect, missing and/or contradictory information.
- *Minor* errors may affect the respondent's comprehension of the translated text and increase the time required to read and understand the translation.
- *Neutral* errors include those that might make the translation a bit harder to understand, but ultimately do not stop the respondent from overall understanding and using the translation in terms of the measurement goal.

In case of several errors per segment, errors could be indicated separately. Assigning errors by post-editors was part of the experiment. In translation practice, post-editing involves correcting raw machine translation output, but no error assignment. It is not possible to preclude that due to additional error assignment, reflecting on corrections influenced the post-editing steps.

One of the important components of a review discussion in the TRAPD approach are comments provided by translators that are the basis for further discussion during the review meeting. It is not possible to export comments provided by translators within MateCat. Therefore, the research team developed an application for documenting the translation process according to the TRAPD methodology. The application retrieved translations and comments from MateCat projects through the MateCat API,

generated spreadsheet files for each step of the translation process (TR1, TR2, and review discussion), and merged them⁶⁹.

The review discussion made use of both the MateCat environment and the initial translations summarized in an Excel file (Figure 4). Everyone, including the reviewers not initiated to the MateCat tool, could prepare for the review session in Excel. Here, both initial translations and potential comments from translators/post-editor had been merged and aligned with the source text. The project manager of the research team hosted the review meeting in Zoom and was responsible for managing all documents and tools. The translation teams could freely discuss which version to copy into MateCat and how to revise it (if applicable). The project manager implemented these actions. By relieving the translation team members from technical and typing activities, all participants could focus on the discussion itself. The project manager ensured the technical functioning of the review discussions, but did not get involved into the discussions content-wise. The combination of MateCat and Excel at the review stage had been chosen due to technical challenges when trying to show two translations of the same source questionnaire (as a so-called translation memory) in MateCat.

FIGURE 4: SCREEN SET-UP DURING THE REVIEW DISCUSSION

⁶⁹ Zavala-Rojas et al.

4. Analytical approach

The unit of analysis in the experiments are the segments of the translated text of a survey question. Each segment is denoted by y_{ij}^k , with $i = 0, 1, \dots, 267$; indicating one out of 268 segments that build up the 40 survey questions sampled from the ESS and the EVS questionnaires. The subscript $j = 0, 1, 2$, indicates that the segment was produced in the control group, first treatment using full post-editing, and the second treatment using light post-editing, respectively. Finally, $k = \{0, 1\}$, where 0 indicates English-German and 1, English-Russian.

To compare the control group against the treatments assessing the quality of these translations, the research team opted for assessing translation quality by coding the errors detected in the translations, and assigning severity levels to such errors. In order to do so, an error scheme was developed. The error coding scheme includes different factors, such as general linguistic features, general translation errors, and also specific challenges of translating the text genre of questionnaires. The research team did not carry out a translation quality assessment of the translations in their entirety (that is, also coding positive or correct translations), but only errors were coded. Therefore, the main dependent variable is defined as the count of such errors, $e_{m(y_{ij})}^k$ relative to every segment, $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$ and is a consecutive natural number counting the errors, and k and y_{ij} link the error to a specific text segment.

A combination of an absolute versus a relative translation quality assessment approach was chosen: Each of the translations was coded by two persons and then the coding outcomes were compared to one another and harmonized in a discussion. There was not one reference translation that would serve as “gold standard”, but all translations were considered at the same level (*absolute* approach). At the same time, in the process of coding, identical errors were identified across different translations. Check backs to previous codings ensured that such errors were coded identically (*relative* approach). The coding was carried out by teams of experts that were not part of the experiments. The codes were automatically retrieved and converted into indicators. A statistical test compared the groups according to their number of errors.

4.1 Error scheme

The error scheme used in this study is based on the harmonised MQM-DQF translation quality metric⁷⁰, which combines the Multidimensional Quality Metric (MQM) developed by the EU-funded QTLaunchPad

⁷⁰ Arle Lommel et al., “Harmonised Metric” 21, no. 645452 (2015): 1–33, <http://www.qt21.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/11/QT21-D3-1.pdf>.

project⁷¹ and the dynamic quality framework (DQF) developed by the Translation Automation User Society (TAUS). The MQM system categorizes many different translation errors, in particular also those done by a machine; it can be tailored to a specific text genre or translation purpose by selecting relevant subsets of errors. While the MQM system was set up as a comprehensive and detailed system, drawing on many different translation metrics, DQF was based on industry best practices and focused on the issues most commonly checked by LSPs. The harmonized metric is a shared error typology, harmonizing meaning and wording of error types where previously deviations had existed.

The team took the DQF subset of MQM and adapted it to the text genre of survey questionnaires and the particular needs of the study, not just by selecting or omitting subcategories but also by adding categories. The original four severity levels, running from critical to neutral, were adapted to the three-level system in the translation tool MateCat, major, minor, neutral: *Major* level of severity means that the translation completely changes the meaning, likely misleads the respondent, or provides incorrect, missing and/or contradictory information. *Minor* errors may affect the respondent's comprehension of the translated text and increase the time required to read and understand the translation. *Neutral* errors include those that might make the translation a bit harder to understand, but ultimately do not stop the respondent from overall understanding and using the translation in terms of the measurement goal. With these error categories, the team tried to integrate considerations of target population reception and potential measurement quality into the assessment - even though aware that this cannot substitute for any empirical testing of an instrument.

Ultimately, the error scheme developed for this research has seven categories: Accuracy, Fluency, Survey-specific terminology/phrases and features, Style, Locale convention, Verity, and Other. Each of these categories is subdivided into subcategories that allow a fine-tuned classification of translation errors in the texts. Table 4 summarises the error scheme definition.⁷²

After having established a final coding for each review output, control and treatment groups were compared on the basis of those errors. The subsections below describe the error scheme and details of the coding process, the definition of the dependent variable, and the modelling approach to compare the control and treatment groups.

⁷¹ "QTLaunchPad" project: <http://www.qt21.eu/launchpad/> (2 December, 2021).

⁷² "Punctuation" and "spelling" were additional sub-categories of "fluency", as in the original error scheme that was used as a model. These categories were coded, too. For the analysis in this report, these categories were taken out, however, since such aspects are typically checked after a review session in additional proof-reading steps.

TABLE 4: ERROR SCHEME: CATEGORIES, SUBCATEGORIES AND DEFINITIONS

Error category	Error subcategory	Definition
Accuracy: The target text does not accurately reflect the source text, allowing for any differences authorized by project-specific specifications.	Addition	The target text includes text not present in the source.
	Omission	Content is missing from the translation that is present in the source.
	Mistranslation	The target content does not accurately represent the source content.
	Over-translation	The target text is more specific than the source text.
	Under-translation	The target text is less specific than the source text.
	Untranslated text	Content that should have been translated has been left in the source language.
	Connotations	A translation may trigger a connotation in the target audience that adds meaning in the translation that is not present in the source text and thus not wanted in the translation.
	Ambiguity	The target text allows different ways of interpretation; the text has more than one meaning.
Fluency: Issues related to the form or content of a text.		
	Grammar	Issues related to the grammar or syntax of the text, other than spelling and punctuation.
	Inconsistency	The target text shows internal inconsistency on different levels, ranging from inconsistent use of repeated survey-specific terminology or phrases over inconsistent use of core terminology to inconsistent use of more general wording.
Survey-specific terminology/phrases and features: Survey-	Mistranslation of survey-specific	The target text does not accurately represent the survey-specific terminology/phrases as used in the target culture.

<p>specific terminology/phrases and features are translated with a term/phrase other than the one expected for the domain or the specific survey conditions.</p>	terminology/phrases	
	Omission of survey-specific terminology/phrases	The target text omits survey-specific terminology/phrases that would be important from a measurement/design point of view.
	Addition of survey-specific terminology/phrases	The target text adds survey-specific terminology/phrases that are not existent in the source.
	Survey mode	Specific needs of a survey mode are not taken into consideration in the translation.
	Scales: Design	Design of scale not correctly rendered in the translation. (a) Differentiation unipolar-bipolar not correctly rendered in translation; (b) symmetry/asymmetry not kept as in the source; (c) answer categories are not kept disjunct (i.e., separate from each other); (d) the level of extremeness ("fixed reference points") is not correctly rendered in translation
	Scales: Distance and intensity	Distances between answer categories/intensity of the answer categories are not correctly rendered in translation. The intervals in the answer scale in the source language bear a specific measurement logic and should not be modified in the translation.
	Scales: Grammar	Grammatical aspects (e.g., relating to genus or numerus) are not taken into consideration in the translation.
	Scales: Inconsistency between question text	A word or phrase used in both the question text and the corresponding answer scale is translated using different words.

	and answer categories	
	Placeholder	Country-placeholder left in brackets or untranslated.
Style: The target text has stylistic problems.	Awkward	The target text is written with an awkward or unidiomatic style. The content is grammatically correct, but not idiomatic.
	Register	The register does not take the target population into account, in terms of their age, education and other relevant socio-demographic characteristics. The register does not correspond to survey-specific style and wording in the target country's survey landscape - e.g., sentence structure is not short, simple and clear, the wording is too complex and/or sophisticated for a questionnaire. Cultural conversational conventions of the target language and culture are not met - e.g. with regard to rules of politeness, forms of addressing, speech acts, etc.
Locale convention: The target text does not adhere to locale-specific mechanical conventions and violates requirements for the presentation of content in the target culture.	Date format	The target text uses a date format inappropriate for its target culture.
	Currency format	The target text uses the wrong format for currency.
	Measurement format	The target text uses a measurement or number format inappropriate for its target culture.
Verity: The target text makes a statement that contradicts the reality of the target culture.	Culture-specific reference	The target text inappropriately uses a culture-specific reference that will not be understandable to the intended audience, since the referred phenomena, behaviour, etc. only exist in the source culture. An adaptation would be required but was not implemented.
Other: Any other issues.		

4.2 Error coding syntax

In order to automatize the comparison of translation errors between versions, the research team defined a systematic error coding syntax, which linked the source text wording to translation errors in the target text. To avoid ambiguity, a vectorised representation of words in a sentence was adopted. In such representation, each word, or *token*, of a given sentence is attributed to a number that corresponds to its position, or index, in the sentence (ranging from 0 to n-1, where n is the number of words in a given sentence). The example below illustrates this vectorised representation:

the red fox jumped over the lazy brown dog

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

After vectorising both source and target segments, a set of rules can be applied to link the source to the translation error in the target language. The error syntax is preceded by the character ‘e’ and composed of two parts separated by a hyphen, where the first part corresponds to the source sentence and the second part to the target sentence. If the error concerns a single wrongfully translated word, it is trivial to represent the error by using the indexes of the words in the source and the target segments. When the error corresponds to a sequence of words, the colon symbol (:) is used to denote the start and end of the problematic expression. The example below illustrates such types of errors. The error that corresponds to the word “red” being translated to Spanish as “verde” (meaning “green” in English) can be seen in green (e1-2), whereas the error for the expression “jumps over” being translated to Spanish as “salta delante del” (meaning “jumps in front of” in English) instead of “saltó sobre el” can be seen in red (e3:4-3:5).

the **red** fox **jumped over** the lazy brown dog

0 **1** 2 **3** **4** 5 6 7 8

el zorro **verde** **salta delante del** perro marrón perezoso

0 1 **2** **3** **4** **5** 6 7 8

e1-2

e3:4-3:5

It is possible to report multiple errors in the same sentence by separating the different errors with a semicolon. Therefore, for the example above, the complete set of errors found in the segment would be coded as **e1-2; e3:4-3:5**. Translation errors can also refer to expressions that are not sequential either in the source or in the target segment. In this case, the same logic hereby described can be applied, but using the plus symbol (+) to denote that the problematic expression is not sequential in the sentence.

Finally, in the case of a given word not existing either in the source or target sentence, the characters ‘na’ are used to represent the absence of the word.

4.3 Error coding process

Coding the errors in the translations resulting from the review sessions was a complex task. In addition to defining the type of error and specifying the words or tokens, coders assigned severity levels to the errors. Below, this deliverable summarizes information about how this process was organised and handled. Later, these error codes could be extracted and processed numerically for calculating statistics of the error categories attributed.

4.3.1 Coders

The research team set up a team-based approach drawing on experiences from other studies^{73,74}. In each language, two independent coders that did not participate in the experiments coded each of the segments included in the set, \mathbf{y} , for potential translation errors, $e_{m(yij)}^k$. They subsequently met with a referee in a harmonization meeting; the referee only got involved when coders could not agree on a final error coding and needed a third person for judgment. The coders were native speakers of the respective languages, trained translators or translation practitioners, and in 3 out of 4 cases highly familiar with survey translation. The lack of familiarity of one of the Russian coders with survey translation was offset by training before the task and by learning by doing through the large number of harmonization sessions. The harmonization process was applied instead of intercoder reliability, as there is evidence suggesting that high intercoder reliability can be difficult to achieve in translation quality assessment, particularly with complex metrics^{75,76,77}. Coder coded the translations without taking into account review comments (if available at all). This way, their approach was independent from any discussion content.

⁷³ Joke Daems, Orphée De Clercq, and Lieve Macken, “Translationese and Post-Editese: How Comparable Is Comparable Quality?,” *Linguistica Antverpiensia* 16 (2017): 89–103, <https://doi.org/10.52034/lansstts.v16i0.434>.

⁷⁴ Maarit Koponen and Leena Salmi, “Post-Editing Quality: Analysing the Correctness and Necessity of Post-Editor Corrections,” *Linguistica Antverpiensia, New Series – Themes in Translation Studies* 16 (January 29, 2017): 137–48, <https://lans-tts.uantwerpen.be/index.php/LANS-TTS/article/view/439/394>.

⁷⁵ Aljoscha Burchardt and Arle Lommel, “Practical Guidelines for the Use of MQM in Scientific Research on Translation Quality,” *Preparation and Launch of a Large-Scale Action for Quality Translation Technology, Report*, 2014, 19.

⁷⁶ Yanfang Jia, Michael Carl, and Xiangling Wang, “Post-Editing Neural Machine Translation versus Phrase-Based Machine Translation for English–Chinese,” *Machine Translation* 33 (2019): 9–29, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10590-019-09229-6>.

⁷⁷ Saldanha and O’Brien, *Res. Methodol. Transl. Stud.*

4.3.2 Referee and project manager

The referee was the same person for both German and Russian, a native speaker of Russian with native speaker level German, and a trained interpreter with a high familiarity in survey translation. The referee had managed both German and Russian review sessions as a project manager and had thus knowledge of the content of the review discussions. Due to this first-hand knowledge, the referee was not chosen as one of the initial coders. Coders were supposed to take a fresh, unbiased look at the translations.

4.3.3 Coders' training

Coders were trained in a virtual training session, including hands-on exercises. In addition, the research team drafted "Instructions for Error Coding" that were shared with all coders - and had been the basis for the virtual coder training.

Relevant information for all coders were:

- guidance on the coding process, that is: how to apply the above-mentioned error scheme and severity levels; examples were included to understand which error categories should be applied to which issues detected;
- information on the error scheme and the coding environment: the coding work was carried out in spreadsheets, one per translation to be assessed (Figure 5). These spreadsheets comprised, each time: the English source text and the translations to be coded, both tokenized in order to be able to clearly point out to which word or sign an error coding would refer; and pre-defined columns in which the error codes as well as the severity levels could be marked by the coders in a uniform and unequivocal manner (see subsection on Error coding syntax).

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X
survey_item_ID	source_text	source_text_comments	source_text_token_count	target_1	target_1_token_count	comments	addition_sev	omission	omission_sev	mistranslation_sev	mistranslation_sev	overtranslation_sev	overtranslation_sev	undertranslation_sev	undertranslation_sev	untranslated	untranslated	connotations	connotations_sev	ambiguous	ambiguous_sev	punctuation	
MTE_G_ERL57	(Refusal)		0: 1; 1 'Refusal'; 2: 1)	(Antwort verweigert)	0: 1; 1 'Antwort'; 2: verweigert'; 3: 1)																		
MTE_G_ERL58	(Don't know)		0: 1; 1 'Don't'; 2: 'know'; 3: 1)	(Weiß nicht)	0: 1; 1 'Weiß'; 2: 'nicht'; 3: 1)																		
MTE_G_ERL59	Please look carefully at the following list of voluntary organisations and activities and say which, if any, do you belong to?		0: Please; 1: look; 2: carefully; 3: at; 4: the; 5: following; 6: list; 7: of; 8: voluntary; 9: organisations; 10: and; 11: activities; 12: and; 13: say; 14: which; 15: ; 16: if; 17: any; 18: ; 19: do; 20: you; 21: belong; 22: to; 23: 1)	Bitte schauen Sie sich die folgende Liste von freiwilligen Organisationen und Aktivitäten an und sagen Sie mir, ob Sie einer oder mehreren davon angehören.	0: Bitte; 1: 'schauen'; 2: 'Sie'; 3: 'sich'; 4: 'die'; 5: 'folgende'; 6: 'Liste'; 7: 'von'; 8: 'freiwilligen'; 9: 'Organisationen'; 10: 'und'; 11: 'Aktivitäten'; 12: 'an'; 13: 'sich'; 14: 'sagen'; 15: 'Sie'; 16: 'mir'; 17: '; 18: 'ob'; 19: 'Sie'; 20: 'einer'; 21: 'oder'; 22: 'mehreren'; 23: 'davon'; 24: 'angehören'; 25: '1)	'freiwillig' does not fit as adjective, rather: 'Freiwilligen-Organisationen' // 'if any' is covered by 'ob'				0-0-0-0													
MTE_G_ERL60	Code all mentioned.		0: Code; 1: all; 2: mentioned; 3: 1)	Alles Zutreffende auswählen.	0: 'Alles'; 1: 'Zutreffende'; 2: auswählen; 3: 1)																		

FIGURE 5: ERROR CODING ENVIRONMENT – EXCEL SPREADSHEET

4.3.4 Harmonization process

The research team developed a Python-based application, based on which the initial codes from the two coders per language (category, severity level, tokenization) could automatically be compared. Differences

were listed in a separate document; this document served as the basis for the harmonization meeting. Typically, the Excel with the highest number of error codes, as became clear from the difference document, was chosen as a basis for the harmonization meeting. In the course of coding, the research team developed an internal document for some universal or language-specific coding decisions to ensure consistency of coding for repeatedly occurring issues.

4.3.5 Challenges in the error coding process

The main challenge in the coding process was to ensure consistency at different levels. As all coders were humans and there is always an idiosyncratic way of understanding language, it needed to be ensured that the results of the coding harmonization meetings (one per review translation, that is, three per language) were as objective and as consistent between one another as possible. Consistency between selecting error types and severity levels needed to be discussed and agreed upon in the harmonization meetings: If a certain translation was attributed a certain error category and severity level, it needed to be made consistent in other translations as well.

For instance: if “the red fox” was translated as “the green fox” in one review version and as “the big fox” in another review version: which error types should be selected - and which severity level? Is selecting another colour more or less severe than selecting another adjective? Selecting error categories and severity levels required a consistent approach across all review translations. Working in a team of three people and not depending on one coder only was the approach to objectivize the coding results as much as possible.

As the different coding harmonization meetings took place with pauses of several days to several weeks in-between, consistency over time was also considered. To ensure consistent error coding over time, the coders, to the extent possible, compared the translations and their codings over time. In addition, for the German language, a few remaining inconsistencies in coding were discussed between the coders and harmonized after all review translations had been coded. In sum, for the error coding to achieve the highest possible quality, a team approach was applied for levelling out subjective idiosyncratic language understanding and inconsistent coding both between review translations and over time (on the importance of consistency in coding, see, e.g., Creswell, J. W., & Creswell⁷⁸). The coding environment in spreadsheets with all source and target texts tokenized proved to be helpful for systematically applying the coding and facilitated later quantitative analyses of the coding results.

⁷⁸ John W. Creswell and J. David Creswell, *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (Sage publications, 2017).

5. Results

5.1 Exploratory analysis

Table 5 presents the total number of errors, $e_{m(yij)}^k$, per group and the number of errors weighted by severity levels. *Neutral* errors were assigned a weight of 1, thus they count as one error. An error considered *minor* was assigned a weight of 1.5 and a *major* error was assigned a weight of 2. The mean of the severity levels is also depicted in the Table 5 a lower number indicates more trivial (neutral) errors. As the majority of errors were of neutral severity, weighting them does not change the relative number of errors in the groups, as will be seen in the next section in the tests for differences across the groups.

TABLE 5: TOTAL ERRORS BY GROUP

Group	Number of errors	Number of errors weighted by severity level	Mean severity level
Control group - German	36	47	1.305556
Control group - Russian	44	66	1.5
Full PE - German	43	53	1.232558
Full PE - Russian	37	53.5	1.445946
Light PE - German	79	98	1.240506
Light PE - Russian	41	56	1.365854

Table 6 depicts the number of errors per category. The appendix depicts the full classification of the errors by subcategories. Groups in the same language are similar to each other, except for the group using light post-editing in German. The majority of errors coded for this group corresponds to the category *Accuracy* and were *neutral*, having a severity mean of 1.17.

TABLE 6: TOTAL ERRORS BY CATEGORY

Group	Error category	Number of errors	Number of errors weighted by severity level	Mean severity level
Control group - German	Accuracy	14	20	1.428571
Control group - German	Fluency	9	9	1
Control group - German	Style	12	17	1.416667
Control group - German	Survey-specific terminology/phrases and features	1	1	1
Control group - Russian	Accuracy	20	35	1.75
Control group - Russian	Fluency	7	9	1.285714
Control group - Russian	Style	13	15.5	1.192308

Control group - Russian	Survey-specific terminology/phrases and features	4	6.5	1.625
Full PE - German	Accuracy	18	26	1.444444
Full PE - German	Fluency	5	5	1
Full PE - German	Style	5	6	1.2
Full PE - German	Survey-specific terminology/phrases and features	15	16	1.066667
Full PE - Russian	Accuracy	13	20	1.538462
Full PE - Russian	Fluency	3	4	1.333333
Full PE - Russian	Style	10	10.5	1.05
Full PE - Russian	Survey-specific terminology/phrases and features	11	19	1.727273
Light PE - German	Accuracy	39	45.5	1.166667
Light PE - German	Fluency	9	10.5	1.166667
Light PE - German	Style	16	22.5	1.40625
Light PE - German	Survey-specific terminology/phrases and features	15	19.5	1.3
Light PE - Russian	Accuracy	12	18.5	1.541667
Light PE - Russian	Fluency	12	15	1.25
Light PE - Russian	Style	8	9.5	1.1875
Light PE - Russian	Survey-specific terminology/phrases and features	9	13	1.444444

A few examples shall help to better understand the results:

- Light PE - German:
 - Source: Now suppose two people from different **race or ethnic** groups each appear in court, charged with an identical crime they did not commit.
 - Target: Nehmen wir an, zwei Menschen unterschiedlicher **ethnischer** Herkunft erscheinen vor Gericht und werden einer gleichen Straftat angeklagt, die sie nicht begangen haben.
 - Error: Register - severity level *major*: "Ethnisch" on its own is difficult to understand for certain groups in society.
- Light PE - German:
 - Source: ...made an **exaggerated** or false insurance claim?
 - Target: ... einen **übertriebenen** oder falschen Versicherungsanspruch geltend gemacht?

- Error: Mistranslation - severity level *minor*: The correct adjective going with “exaggerated insurance claim” (collocation) would be “überzogen.”
- Control Group - German:
 - Source: To be a good **citizen**, how important would you say it is for a person to...
 - Target: Um ein guter **Bürger** zu sein, wie wichtig ist es Ihrer Meinung nach, dass eine Person ...
 - Error: Overtranslation - severity level *neutral*: It would have been more appropriate to add the female term for citizen as well.
- Control group - Russian:
 - Source: Please tell me, for each one, whether you think it is very important, rather important or not very important for a **successful** marriage?
 - Target: Скажите, пожалуйста, по каждому пункту, считаете ли Вы его очень важным, скорее важным или не очень важным для **счастливого** брака?
 - Error: Over-translation - severity level *major*: translation of the word successful is more specific in the target text (the word was translated as happy).
- Full PE - Russian
 - Source: **Not at all**
 - Target: **Нисколько**
 - Error: Scales Inconsistency - severity level *minor*: the word “Нисколько” is difficult to interpret out of context. The option “Вообще не выполняете” (Never do it) would be better and also fit to the question text.
- Light PE - Russian
 - Source: 5 times **or** more
 - Target: 5 раз **и** более
 - Error: Mistranslation - severity level *neutral*: the word “or” was translated as “and” (и).

5.2 Main results

The team compared the control group against the treatments in two ways. Firstly, the team used *z-score* tests for two population proportions. This test assesses whether two groups (e.g., text outputs in the control group in German and text outputs produced with machine translation and light post-editing) differ significantly on some single characteristic; in this case, the number of errors.

The test compared the proportion of errors in the text segments by the control group against the group using light post-editing. A second test compared the proportion of errors in the control group against the group using full post-editing. As both treatments share the same control group, multiple comparisons using *z-score* tests carry the risk of increasing Error Type I. Therefore, the second strategy to compare

the groups was to run a *Poisson regression* for the counts of errors. Both *z-score* tests and Poisson regressions show similar and consistent results. This section presents the results of both types of tests⁷⁹.

5.2.1 z-score tests

A *z-score* test statistic for $H_0: p_1 - p_2 = 0$ is defined as follows:

$$\frac{(\bar{p}_1 - \bar{p}_2) - 0}{\sqrt{\bar{p}(1 - \bar{p})\left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2}\right)}}$$

where, \bar{p}_1 represents the ratio of the errors in the control group divided by the total number of segments. \bar{p}_2 is the ratio of the errors in the treatment group divided by the total number of segments.

$n_1 = n_2 = 268$, the total number of text segments. Finally, \bar{p} is the total proportion of errors, calculated as the sum of the errors of the control and treatment groups divided by $n_1 + n_2$. Table 7 shows the results of *z-score* tests comparing control groups and treatments, it also shows the tests for the errors weighted by severity level and for unweighted errors.

TABLE 7: RESULTS OF Z-SCORE TEST COMPARING CONTROL GROUP AND TREATMENTS PER LANGUAGE. WEIGHTED AND UNWEIGHTED DATA

Comparison	Language	\bar{p}_1	\bar{p}_2	z-statistic	P value	Confidence interval lower boundary	Confidence interval higher boundary	Errors weighted by severity
Human translation vs MT & full-PE	German	0.134328	0.160448	0.534471	0.464733	-0.08983	0.037592	No
		0.175373	0.197761	0.307339	0.579317	-0.09205	0.047275	Yes

⁷⁹ The preprocessing of the data was done in Python 3.7.6, the tests and regressions were done in RStudio 1.3.1093 that runs R 4.0.2

Human translation vs MT & light-PE	German	0.134328	0.294776	19.52915	9.91E-06	-0.23234	-0.08855	No
		0.175373	0.365672	23.63524	1.16E-06	-0.2675	-0.1131	Yes
Human translation vs MT & full-PE	Russian	0.164179	0.13806	0.523565	0.469325	-0.03821	0.090453	No
		0.246269	0.199627	1.424222	0.23271	-0.02745	0.120735	Yes
Human translation vs MT & light-PE	Russian	0.164179	0.152985	0.055928	0.813052	-0.05438	0.076767	No
		0.246269	0.208955	0.859587	0.353854	-0.03734	0.111967	Yes

EXPERIMENTS IN THE GERMAN LANGUAGE

The number of errors in the group using only human translation in German (control group) is not significantly different to the number errors in the group using machine translation and *full* post-editing. This result does not change when the errors are weighted by severity level. With respect to the number errors in the final review translation, both translation outputs are of the same quality, and H0 cannot be rejected.

In the case of the group using machine translation and *light* post-editing, there is a significant difference in the number of errors in comparison with the control group, and this difference is maintained when the errors are weighted by severity. The data allows to reject H0, and supports the alternative hypothesis, that is, the final review output has more errors when machine translation and light post-editing was used.

EXPERIMENTS IN THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

In the case of the experiments in Russian, H0 cannot be rejected, as the difference in the number of errors in the group using only human translation is not statistically significant in comparison with the group using machine translation and full post-editing or light post-editing.

Overall, experiments in German and Russian show positive results towards the use of machine translation and full post-editing at the initial translation stage, as this method yields equivalent results to human translation, when the output of the review sessions is considered, not the actual outcome of machine translation.

In the case of the text outputs produced by the use of machine translation and light post-editing, results are positive in the Russian language, but negative in German, the translations had a larger proportion of errors. The mean severity of the errors indicated in Table 7 for this group (1.17) indicates that this method resulted in many neutral errors, therefore machine translation and full post-editing is preferable.

5.3 Regression analysis

The Poisson regression model is defined as

$$\log(\lambda_i) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_i$$

Where $e_{m(yij)}^k \sim$ Poisson with λ_i , for x_i , where x_i is a categorical predictor with three values describing the group from which the counts (errors) are estimated. Groups, x_i , correspond to control group, light post-editing and full post-editing, and k , characterizes the target language. In this way, the regression compares at the same time both treatments against the control group. Models are run per language and as in the case of the *z-score* tests, the research team ran models for the unweighted data and the data weighted by severity levels. Both models show consistent results. Poisson regression coefficients are interpreted as the difference or ratio between the log of the expected counts, in other words, for a one-unit change in the predictor variable – in this specific regression, for a change of group category - the difference in the logs of expected counts is expected to change by the respective regression coefficient, given other predictors held constant. The rate at which events occur is called incidence rate, incidence rate ratios are obtained by exponentiating the coefficients. The results of the regression are shown in Table 8.

TABLE 8: RESULTS OF THE POISSON REGRESSION MODEL

Language	Coefficient name	Coefficient estimate	Standard error	Statistic	P value	Confidence interval lower boundary	Confidence interval higher boundary	Errors weighted by severity levels
German	(Intercept)	3.583519	0.166666	21.50	0.00000	3.238052	3.893314	No
	full post-editing	0.177681	0.225906	0.79	0.43156	-0.264	0.625187	
	light post-editing	0.785929	0.201087	3.91	0.00009	0.400195	1.191121	
German	(Intercept)	3.850148	0.145865	26.40	0.00000	3.54996	4.12304	Yes
	full post-editing	0.120144	0.200361	0.60	0.54875	-0.27228	0.515665	

	light post-editing	0.73482	0.177428	4.14	0.00003	0.393272	1.090608	
Russian	(Intercept)	3.78419	0.150756	25.10	0.00000	3.473414	4.065802	No
	full post-editing	-0.17327	0.223057	-0.78	0.43727	-0.61498	0.262896	
	light post-editing	-0.07062	0.217066	-0.33	0.74493	-0.49874	0.355367	
Russian	(Intercept)	4.189655	0.123091	34.04	0.00000	3.938292	4.421581	Yes
	full post-editing	-0.20997	0.183965	-1.14	0.25371	-0.5738	0.1493	
	light post-editing	-0.1643	0.181683	-0.90	0.36581	-0.52308	0.190996	

EXPERIMENTS IN GERMAN LANGUAGE

The expected mean of number of errors in the group using only human translation in German is significantly different from the number of errors in the group using machine translation and light post-editing, but it is not significantly different to the group using full post-editing. This result does not change when the errors are weighted by severity level. Both models predict similar results; the intercept point estimate is also similar. It is possible to predict the number of additional error units due to this effect by calculating the incidence rate ratio; this statistic is defined by the following for the unweighted data:

$$f(0.7859) = e^{0.7859} = 2.1944$$

And as the following for the weighted data:

$$f(0.7348) = e^{0.7348} = 2.085$$

This implies that changing from the control group to the treatment using machine translation and light post-editing, the error count is expected to increase in 2 units.

EXPERIMENTS IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

In the case of the experiments in the Russian language, the expected count of errors does not change when the group changes from control to machine translation and light post-editing or full post-editing. This means that there are no statistically significant differences in the number of translation errors in texts produced by human translation in comparison to texts produced by machine translation and a form of post-editing.

7. Conclusion and discussion

The main research question that motivated this study was: Is the quality of the final translated output after the Review meeting affected by introducing machine translation and post-editing into the TRAPD procedure? If so, are the effects negative or positive for the outputs' quality?

The results of this pilot study are overall positive for the use of a combination of human translation and post-edited machine translation in the translation of survey questionnaires with the TRAPD approach. The specific experiments reported here - for the German and Russian languages and for a sample of ESS and EVS survey questions - show evidence that the translation quality of the final review output is hardly affected by introducing machine translation and post-editing at the initial translation stage, in combination with human translation. In the specific setting described in this report, the effect of including machine translation and post-editing into TRAPD was barely quantifiable when comparing it to the human control setting. Specific experiments, however, cannot be generalized out of the context in which the tests took place.

More specific research questions assessed group dependencies of the effect of machine translation and post-editing: Are Russian and German translations affected differently? And, are the differences conditional on the use of light or full post-editing?

The answer to the first question is, yes, the effects of machine translation and post-editing are different between Russian and German, and yes, there are different effects depending on the type of post-editing used. In the Russian language, the quality of texts using machine translation and post-editing cannot be distinguished from the quality that derives from using human translation only. In the German language, there is an increase in the number of errors when light post-editing is used; however, the predicted increase of such errors is 2 units. This cannot be considered an increase of such magnitude that rules out the use of the method.

In the experiments, machine translation combined with post-editing was implemented by participants whose background is in social sciences. Overall, looking at the experimental results, this seemed to work, but a detailed analysis on the post-editing step is needed for more insights.

The text outputs analysed in this report are those considered final after the committee meeting, that is, at the review step in the TRAPD approach. Harkness and other proponents of the TRAPD argued that the review sessions in which the team discusses translation options are fundamental to translation quality. The findings of the present study show that the committee meeting is a very important aspect of the TRAPD, as the potential effect of methods used to produce the parallel translations in the T step do not remain in the final outputs.

When answering the research questions, the team implicitly assumed that the human translation from the control group is the best one. For Russian, this did not apply; the control group translation involving only human translations was in fact the Russian translation with the highest error count, in both the

unweighted and the weighted measurement. Lack of significantly different results in the experiments can therefore be interpreted as similar quality in all translation settings.

The team coded every single instance of an error; hence, the error count per team does not necessarily stand for unique errors but may be inflated through repeated errors, e.g. through errors re-occurring across repeated agree-disagree scales or an erroneous term that is used several times within the same item.

The way the severity levels were defined included assessing a potential impact of erroneous wordings on respondents - and in this case, also on interviewers since the experiment was framed as a face-to-face interview. Assigning severity levels was therefore challenging and can be subjective, even when discussed in a team. The impact might have been over- or underrated, when choosing severity levels. However, since a consistent error coding approach was applied across all review translations and since coders were not knowledgeable of which review version they were coding, no translation should be put at a disadvantage through the assessment. Furthermore, the analyses, conducted both without and with weights according to error types, came to the same conclusions, which is positive for the project results.

Given the high number of errors in each team, it has to be acknowledged that, in a real-life translation setting, teams would certainly have picked up further errors when implementing the questionnaire in a survey tool and testing the questionnaire in simple dry runs or quantitative/qualitative pre-tests (as the full TRAPD model recommends); also, there was no room for additional proof-reading beyond the context of the review discussions or the possibility to clarify source text issues with the developers. Hence, while one can compare translations across the experiments (the goal in this study), one cannot state that the translations produced in this experiment would indeed be the translations that teams would sign off after further quality control steps in the real world.

Finally, while with the research presented here, conclusions can be drawn on the overall team approach and how machine translation and post-editing work within this setting, it is not possible to draw conclusions on how much the post-edited versions indeed contributed to the final review output. As outputs of team review sessions build strongly on the dynamics of such discussions, it is to be analysed in further research (see outlook) to what extent the positive outcome was due to the HAMT, the other (human) translation or to other factors contributing to the meeting dynamics, such as the participants' experience or expertise in questionnaire translation, development and wording. Furthermore, future research can look into the process of the review discussion itself, whether this was influenced by integrating HAMT. The overall outcome of this study - that the inclusion of HAMT in a team approach for producing a questionnaire translation is overall promising and yields translations of similar quality as team sessions only involving human translations - is not based on the direct output of machine translation, post-edited by social scientists, but on the outcome of a team discussion of three experts.

7.1 Outlook

Overall, this research project shows positive results for the use of machine translation and post-editing in combination with human translation. In order to arrive at a conclusion about the potential effects of introducing HMT in the TRAPD, comprehensive analyses with an interdisciplinary perspective are required. In addition to this report, the team is working on several other publications: for instance, Behr et al. study specific elements (e.g., terminology, fills, response categories) that had driven the source item selection process in the first place and trace back where the review translation for these came from, that is, from the human-translated version, the post-edited version or the review discussion itself (Behr et al.). The work by Sorato et al. focuses on the quality of the raw machine translation outputs, i.e. texts produced by a machine translation engine before post-editing, through the use of similarity metrics and a Quality Estimation (QE) framework. Dorer et al. focus on cognitive aspects based on the transcripts from the review sessions to study the effect of the experimental conditions on the review *process*, not only on the text outputs. Future research should focus on expanding the number of languages, as in this pilot study it was only possible to include target languages.

7.2 Study within the wider context of SSHOC

The research presented in the deliverable was produced in the spirit of SSHOC by bringing together social scientists, translation scholars, and computer linguists. Machine translation is (as of yet) primarily used in the translation industry; its steep and continuous quality improvements over the past years have resulted in many new users across disciplines, including social scientists, even though the use among the latter may not yet reach the proficiency level of translation practitioners. This project bridges the divide between the worlds of translation and social sciences, aiming to support research infrastructure in their sound and considerate uptake of these new technological developments.

Since key machine translation engines (e.g., Google Translate or deepL) are freely available to everyone, the project embodies the SSHOC core value of open accessibility. Moreover, following the FAIR principles of data science, all data of this unique translation experiment will be made available in a data repository to support the principles of open science, linked in the SSHOC marketplace, and therefore integrated in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Other researchers can thus exploit the research data for their own research questions and thus improve data collection methods in cross-national and cross-cultural studies.

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9. Appendix

TABLE 9: ERRORS BY GROUP AND SUBCATEGORY

Group	Error subcategory	Number of errors	Number of errors weighted by severity level	Mean severity level
Control group - German	Awkward	3	4	1.333333
Control group - German	Ambiguity	2	2.5	1.25
Control group - German	Grammar	7	7	1
Control group - German	Inconsistency	2	2	1
Control group - German	Mistranslation	5	8	1.6
Control group - German	Omission	3	4.5	1.5
Control group - German	Omission of survey-specific terminology/phrases	1	1	1
Control group - German	Over-translation	4	5	1.25
Control group - German	Register	9	13	1.444444
Control group - Russian	Addition	5	7.5	1.5
Control group - Russian	Awkward	12	14.5	1.208333
Control group - Russian	Ambiguity	1	2	2
Control group - Russian	Grammar	3	3.5	1.166667
Control group - Russian	Inconsistency	4	5.5	1.375
Control group - Russian	Mistranslation	5	8	1.6
Control group - Russian	Omission	3	5.5	1.833333
Control group - Russian	Over-translation	6	12	2
Control group - Russian	Register	1	1	1
Control group - Russian	Scales: design	1	2	2
Control group - Russian	Scales: grammar	2	2.5	1.25
Control group - Russian	Scales: inconsistency	1	2	2
Full PE - German	Awkward	4	4.5	1.125
Full PE - German	Ambiguity	2	2.5	1.25
Full PE - German	Grammar	3	3	1
Full PE - German	Inconsistency	2	2	1
Full PE - German	Mistranslation of survey-specific terminology/phrases	1	1.5	1.5
Full PE - German	Mistranslation	9	14.5	1.611111
Full PE - German	Omission	4	5	1.25

Full PE - German	Omission of survey-specific terminology/phrases	1	1.5	1.5
Full PE - German	Over-translation	3	4	1.333333
Full PE - German	Placeholder	1	1	1
Full PE - German	Register	1	1.5	1.5
Full PE - German	Scales: distance	10	10	1
Full PE - German	Scales: grammar	2	2	1
Full PE - Russian	Awkward	10	10.5	1.05
Full PE - Russian	Ambiguity	2	2.5	1.25
Full PE - Russian	Grammar	1	1	1
Full PE - Russian	Inconsistency	2	3	1.5
Full PE - Russian	Mistranslation of survey-specific terminology/phrases	6	12	2
Full PE - Russian	Mistranslation	6	10	1.666667
Full PE - Russian	Omission	1	2	2
Full PE - Russian	Over-translation	1	1.5	1.5
Full PE - Russian	Scales: grammar	2	3	1.5
Full PE - Russian	Scales: inconsistency	3	4	1.333333
Full PE - Russian	Under-translation	3	4	1.333333
Light PE - German	Awkward	4	5.5	1.375
Light PE - German	Ambiguity	2	2.5	1.25
Light PE - German	Grammar	9	10.5	1.166667
Light PE - German	Mistranslation of survey-specific terminology/phrases	4	5.5	1.375
Light PE - German	Mistranslation	9	13.5	1.5
Light PE - German	Omission	1	1	1
Light PE - German	Omission of survey-specific terminology/phrases	2	2.5	1.25
Light PE - German	Over-translation	27	28.5	1.055556
Light PE - German	Register	12	17	1.416667
Light PE - German	Scales: design	1	1.5	1.5
Light PE - German	Scales: grammar	2	2	1
Light PE - German	Scales: inconsistency	6	8	1.333333
Light PE - Russian	Addition	1	2	2
Light PE - Russian	Awkward	6	7	1.166667
Light PE - Russian	Grammar	3	4.5	1.5
Light PE - Russian	Inconsistency	9	10.5	1.166667
Light PE - Russian	Mistranslation	5	6.5	1.3
Light PE - Russian	Omission	3	4.5	1.5

Light PE - Russian	Omission of survey-specific terminology/phrases	1	1	1
Light PE - Russian	Over-translation	3	5.5	1.833333
Light PE - Russian	Register	2	2.5	1.25
Light PE - Russian	Scales: grammar	5	7.5	1.5
Light PE - Russian	Scales: inconsistency	3	4.5	1.5

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